

Leukodystrophy in Children: 12 Cases

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Leukodystrophies are a rare genetic disease characterized by damage of the myelin sheath. They represent a large number of diseases that are heterogeneous by their clinical and neuropathological aspects.

Material and Methods: We report 12 cases of leukodystrophies collected at the Neuropediatric Unit of Abderrahim Harouchi Mother and Child Hospital CHU Ibn Rochd, Casablanca, Morocco. **Results:** The average age of diagnosis was 2 years and 9 months, with a predominance of females (sex ratio:0.33). Consanguinity was found in 5 cases. The onset symptomatology was dominated by psychomotor regression, found in 8 patients, and seizures in 4 patients. Motor signs were in the foreground: pyramidal syndrome in 5 cases, hypotonia in 4 cases, tetraparesis in 1 case, dysarthria in 1 case. The lumbar puncture, carried out in 4 patients, revealed hyperproteinorachy in 3 cases, glycorachy and cytological study were normal. We noted a decreased level of Arylsulfatase A in 6 cases. Imaging was performed in all patients and showed diffuse white matter demyelination. MRI allowed us to classify our cases and showed 7 cases of metachromatic leukodystrophy, 1 case of cavitory leukodystrophy, 1 case of Refsum disease, 1 case of Canavan disease, 1 case of Cockayne syndrome and 1 case of adrenoleukodystrophy. The electroneuromyogram showed a decrease in nerve conduction velocities in 2 cases. Molecular study was performed in one patient finding a heterozygous mutation.

Conclusion: The diagnosis of leukodystrophies is often difficult because of their clinical heterogeneity. The partnership of clinicians with geneticists may be the key point to improve diagnosis and therapeutic management.

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INTRODUCTION

Leukodystrophies (LD) are defined as genetic, primary diseases affecting the white matter (WM) of the central nervous system (CNS) and sometimes also the peripheral nervous system (PNS).

The concept of LD gradually emerged from the study of diffuse cerebral sclerosis (HEUBNER 1887). They are characterized by disturbances in myelin formation (4), leading to the production of abnormal myelin responsible for demyelination. Onset varies from birth to adulthood but is most common in children (3). The clinical presentation includes neurological signs associated with progressive demyelination. Diagnosis of the disease has significantly benefited from advances in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and molecular biology. MRI

can suggest the diagnosis in individuals with a suggestive neurological presentation. The advancements in molecular biology now enable the detection of mutations responsible for the disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We conducted a descriptive retrospective study of 12 cases of LD collected over a 4-year period (January 2019 - January 2023) in the Neuropediatric Unit, Abderrahim Harouchi Mother-Child Hospital of Casablanca University Hospital.

RESULTS

In our series, the mean age at diagnosis of these patients was 2 years and 9 months, ranging from 6 months to 7

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years. The majority were girls (75%). In their medical history, consanguinity was noted in 5 cases, and a similar symptomatology in the family in 3 cases. Early symptoms were dominated by psychomotor regression in 8 patients

and convulsions in 4. Motor signs included pyramidal syndrome in 5 cases, hypotonia in 4, tetraparesis, and dysarthria in 1 (Figure 1).

● Pyramidal ● Hypotonia ● Tetraparesis ● Dysarthria

Figure 1: Clinical findings

Paraclinical findings:

Lumbar puncture, performed in 4 patients, revealed hyperproteinorachia in 3 cases. Glycorrachia and cytological studies were normal. Arylsulfatase A assay was performed in 6 cases, showing decreased levels in all 6. MRI was conducted in all patients, revealing diffuse demyelinating white matter and white matter hypersignal in T2 sequences (Figure 2 - 3). This examination was also used to determine the nature of the leukodystrophy, revealing: 7 cases of metachromatic LD, 1 case of cavitory LD, 1 case of Refsum disease, 1 case of Canavan disease, 1 case of Cockayne syndrome, and 1 case of

adrenoleukodystrophy (confirmed by a high C24/C22 ratio).

Electroneuromyograms showed reduced nerve conduction velocities in 2 cases. Molecular studies in one patient revealed a hyccin mutation. Management primarily relies on symptomatic treatment, including rehabilitation, re-education, and comfort care prescribed for all patients. Anticonvulsant therapy was initiated in the four patients who developed convulsions, two of whom were on dual therapy. Clinical signs stabilized in nine patients, while three were lost to follow-up.

Figure 2: Cerebral MRI, Supra and infratentorial white matter signal change related to the metachromatic leukodystrophy

Figure 3: Cerebral MRI, High signal area in the supratentorial periventricular white matter related to the metachromatic leukodystrophy

DISCUSSION

LDs are a group of genetic, progressive, metabolic diseases that can affect the entire nervous system. Each

type of leukodystrophy is caused by a specific genetic abnormality leading to abnormal development or

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destruction of the white matter (myelin sheath), responsible for demyelination.

LDs can be classified into different categories:

- LDs of the peroxisomal disease group:
 - Adrenoleukodystrophy (ALD) / Adrenomyeloneuropathy (AMN).
 - Adult Refsum disease.
- Zellweger spectrum diseases / Neonatal adrenoleukodystrophy / Infantile Refsum disease.
- LD of the lysosomal disease group:
 - Metachromal leukodystrophy (MDL)
 - Krabbe disease.
- LD of the cavitory type:
 - Alexander's disease/Canavan's disease/CACH syndrome/Megalencephalic leukodystrophy with subcortical cysts (or MLC).
 - Hypomyelinating LD: Pelizaeus-Merzbacher disease (or PMD) / Pelizaeus-Merzbacher-like disease - Spastic paraplegia 2 / Hypomyelination and congenital cataract (or HCC).

Unclassified or undetermined LD.

LDs are rare diseases, and their overall incidence is difficult to assess due to the challenges in diagnosis. A study conducted in Germany by the pediatric department of the University of Hamburg in 1997 (5) reported that the general incidence of LD is estimated at 2.0/100,000 births. In our context, the incidence cannot be specified due to the lack of epidemiological studies.

Consanguinity plays a significant role. In our series, three patients came from consanguineous marriages, with two presenting similar family histories. Compared with the literature, in an Indian series of metachromal leukodystrophy (MDL), 70% of patients were from consanguineous marriages, with four similar family

histories. In other series, consanguinity was present in all patients.

(7-8)

Symptomatology in LD typically appears after a free interval, with the onset of psychomotor regression. Motor impairment is common, leading to delayed achievement of motor milestones or motor regression (10). Hypotonia may manifest as peripheral neuropathy in the early stages but can transition to spasticity later. Cognitive impairment is prevalent, and seizures may occur early or later in the disease course. (11)

Peripheral neuropathy with diminished deep tendon reflexes may be an early sign, posing a diagnostic challenge and potentially being mistaken for other conditions such as Guillain-Barré syndrome (11). The diagnostic pathway for LD involves a comprehensive assessment of history, psychomotor development, clinical examination, and paraclinical examinations, including MRI and genetic studies.

Cerebral MRI is a sensitive diagnostic tool for detecting white matter abnormalities. Different MRI sequences provide valuable information, and recent studies suggest systematic analysis of white matter signal abnormalities in different sequences could aid diagnosis. (12)

In this sense, one classification proposes to divide LDs into two subtypes according to the results of cerebral MRI [13]:

Hypomyelinating LDs, in which a slight hyperintensity of the cerebral white matter is evident on the MRI T2-sequence, and the T1-sequence shows no exclusive pattern of intensity in terms of intensity, and is generally isolated from the cerebral cortex.

Demyelinating LD, in which significant T2 hyperintensity and significant T1 hypointensity can be detected.

Figure 4 cerebral MRI

- (a) Demyelinating leukodystrophy T2-weighted sequences showed asymmetric multifocal white matter damage (white arrows).
- (b) hypomyelinating leukodystrophy) was identified. A confluent, mild T1-weighted hypointensity (left image) and a mild T2-weighted hypersignal (right image) were detected.
- (c) Demyelinating leukodystrophy was diagnosed. A prominent confluent T1-weighted hypointensity (left image) and a prominent T2-weighted hypersignal (right image).

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Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) can distinguish between various white matter abnormalities, with specific patterns associated with certain LDs (14-15). Advances in genetic study and high-throughput sequencing

technologies have revolutionized the molecular diagnosis of inherited white matter disorders. (16) Several mutations are described in LD (Table 1)

Table 1 : Types of leukodystrophy with the genetic mutation

LD	Transmission	Gene
Pelizaeus-Merzbacher	X linked	PLP1 gene
LD with GJA12	Autosomal recessive	Gja12/GJC2 gene
LD with hyccine	Autosomal recessive	FAM126A gene
LD with Hsp60	Autosomal recessive	HSPD1 gene
LD with MCT8	Recessive X linked	SCL16A2 gene
18q syndrome	Sporadic	18q- Deletion
LD with SOX10	Autosomal dominant	SOX10 gene
H-ABC syndrome	Sporadic	
LD with metaphysary chondrodysplasia	X linked	Locus Xq 25-q27
4H syndrome	Autosomal recessive	PoIIIA & PoIIB

Morocco's population is highly inbred, increasing the risk of autosomal recessive LD.

LD in its autosomal recessive forms. The use of genetic studies remains difficult due to the cost and accessibility of molecular biology techniques. Comprehensive assessment of clinical findings, brain magnetic resonance imaging and genetic studies play a key role in the early diagnosis of people with LD.

No cure is available for most hereditary white matter disorders, but preventive and symptomatic preventive and symptomatic care can increase quality of life and extend the lifespan of children with LD

This treatment is based on rehabilitation and re-education in the face of major symptoms: swallowing disorders, spasticity and joint deformities, which improve gross and fine motor skills as well as cognitive functions in affected individuals [13]. Nutritional support is also essential for LD children, but can be difficult due to the inability to feed and swallowing difficulties. Follow-up by nutritionists and speech therapists can help improve these patients' quality of life.

Bone marrow transplantation, when performed early in the course of the disease, before signs of neurological deterioration appear, can stabilize or reverse demyelinating brain lesions by replacing damaged microglial cells with healthy ones [11]. In some people with MDL, this therapy can halt central nervous system damage (with electrophysiological evidence), prevent

mental deterioration and improve IQ [17]. However, cohort studies have shown that in patients with the juvenile form of MDL, demyelination continues to progress after bone marrow transplantation in 31% of cases. This phenomenon could be attributed to late initiation of treatment [18].

Gene therapy using autologous CD34+ cells, which are enriched from patients' bone marrow or mobilized peripheral blood and transduced with a lentiviral vector that inserts one or more copies of the human ARSA gene, so that the genetically modified cells become capable of expressing the functional ARSA enzyme (LIBMELDY). It is a therapeutic option only for asymptomatic children with no clinical manifestations of the disease, in terms of motor, cognitive and/or behavioral impairment, suffering from the late infantile or early juvenile form of MDL. In other children within the scope of LIBMELDY's marketing authorization, corresponding to symptomatic children with early clinical manifestations of the disease, suffering from the early juvenile form of MDL, even if they have retained the ability to walk independently and before the onset of cognitive decline. The HAS Transparency Commission considers that LIBMELDY has no place in the therapeutic strategy [19].

CONCLUSION

LDs are rare genetic diseases with complex diagnostic challenges. Collaboration between clinicians and medical

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geneLcists is crucial for accurate diagnosis. Although no cure exists, symptomaLc care and intervenLons such as rehabilitaLion, nutriLonal support, and bone marrow transplantaLion can improve the quality of life and extend lifespan in affected individuals. Gene therapy remains a promising area of research, but its clinical applicaLion requires further evaluaLion.

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